

THE TEACHER'S ROLE FOR THE PERSONAL HYGIENE BEHAVIOR OF CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract:

The aim of the research is to know the teacher's role and teacher's needs in the personal hygiene learning of children with cerebral palsy. The subject of the research is teachers of SLB D1 YPAC Surakarta as a respondents are 6 persons. Data gathering technique gets from interview and observation. Data will be analyzed with qualitative research method in descriptive approach. The result of the research indicate that the majority respondents who is using speech method to convey about the personal hygiene learning. From 6 respondents, only 1 respondent who is sometimes using demonstration method. Utilizing picture media sometimes use by all respondents, 2 respondents sometimes using another media. From all respondents said that need another learning media which is might support the succeed of the personal hygiene learning of children with cerebral palsy.

Keywords: teacher's role, personal hygiene behaviour, cerebral palsy

Introduction

The awareness of personal hygiene importance is often forgotten in daily activities. 'Personal Hygiene' comes from Greek. Personal means individual and hygiene means health. Personal hygiene is an action to keep hygiene and individual health for physically and psychologically prosperity (Wartunah & Tarwoto, 2004:59). Personal hygiene is a part of daily living and it's a personal responsibility, so it is proper that we concern to our personal hygiene in order to avoid from many kind of disease. It also occur to children with cerebral palsy. Cerebral palsy is a type of 'brain injury', it's a condition that influence motoric neural control system as a consequence of brain lesion

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or a neuromuscular disease which caused by developmental disorder or the damage of the part of brain which is connected to the motoric function controller (Sumantri, 1996:99). For the common children, personal hygiene behavior might not be a problem in their activity. Notoadmojo (2003:12) explained that 'behavior is an activity or a deed of one organism that can be observed or even learned'. Personal hygiene behavior is an understanding, attitude, and practice which is do by someone in order increase their healthy degree, to maintain self hygiene, to increase self esteem, to create a beauty, and to avoid incidence of disease.

Different with children with cerebral palsy, caused by anomaly symptom of children with cerebral palsy directly impact to: '(1) the existence of mobilization disorder, (2) the existence of ADL disorder, (3) the existence of communication disorder, (4) the existence of mental function, (5) the existence of sensory disorder. (Salim, 1996:127-128). The get neural obstruction on their mobilization, that makes obstruction of doing ADL, they get communication disorder, so they can't say what they wanted, they have mental function disorder which influences to their intelligence also have sensory disorder. The impact of that various disorders, they get obstruction to do their own hygiene activity without other's help in their environment. It makes possible if the children condition in their daily school seems less hygiene. From the researcher observation, find that the children have dry hair n damage, in indicates they seldom washing their hair n less care, less teeth hygiene, and smelly mouth as effect of rare brushing teeth and less clean when cleaning spittle, the nails are long and dirty because they're not cutting their nails routine, and the hands hygiene have less attention, the ears and skin's fold looks dirty as an effect of bathing unwell. Beside that, in the daily, children with wheelchair often have a dirty hands, children who like to drooling also influence to their face hygiene and smelly mouth beside they seldom brush their teeth. Washing hands before and after meals behavior are often forgotten.

Parents and teachers function around the children extremely influence to their healthy hygiene level. In school environment, teacher has a function in ADL learning, beside teaching they also have responsible to remind the children about it. The awareness about hygiene behavior need to be inculcated to the children since early age. Keep healthy and hygiene behavior can be increase by practicing and inuring about any kind of self caring form. Such as a research from Nurjanah, Rahmawati, and Nurlita (2011) in Personal Hygiene of The Students of Jatinangor Elementary School shows that personal hygiene respondents are still below, so need intervention from parents and teachers at school to educate and give information about personal hygiene, which helped by medical officer of related health service through School Health Exertion program.

From the research of 6 SLB D1 YPAC Surakarta teachers, by interviews and observation, most of them said that they have difficulty to extend the personal hygiene subject, it caused by low intelligence level which is the impact of their disability. During this time, the teacher extends the subject only by teacher's handbook, there's no other handbook or other media. Teacher can only use picture media to support learning activity, using speech method still dominant in that learning process. Only 1 teacher that sometime using demonstration method in personal hygiene learning.

By observing children with cerebral palsy condition and the discussion above, researcher feel challenged to try creating learning media which can link with process of extending the subject of personal hygiene learning to the children with cerebral palsy. The aim is to understanding children about the subject and they're willing to do it routinely. Such as Adhi (2015) from IKIP Saraswati Tabanan, research about Character Education Model Based On Storytelling. The result shows that storytelling is rich of local character education values, if it gives on the right ways, it will dispose shapes the children character to be good. From that, children know about character (to know), can feel the character value (to feel), and able to apply a character (to act). So from storytelling, character education can be plant to the students.

This research has a purpose to know the teacher's role and needs in personal hygiene learning to the children with cerebral palsy in SLB D1 YPAC Surakarta. From this research, researcher try to find the teacher's difficulties in self hygiene learning and also to know the teacher's need about the importance of learning media to support learning activity.

Research Method

This research using qualitative research method. Research subject as respondents are teacher who teach in SLB D1 YPAC Surakarta, counted 6 persons. Data withdrawal technique by interview and observation. The data which gets then analyzed by qualitative descriptive.

Result And Discussion

Result

Based on the data gathering result by interview and observation, show that:

1. Using speech method in *personal hygiene* learning

Table 1: Using speech method *personal hygiene* learning

No	Frequency Level	Quantity	Percentage
1	Always	6	100%
2	Seldom	0	0%
3	Never	0	0%
Total		6	100%

From the data gathering result using speech method in personal hygiene learning, get data that from 6 respondents, all respondents always use speech method. If it served in diagram, will be like this below;

Picture 1: Speech method using in personal hygiene learning

2. Demonstration method using in personal hygiene learning

Table 2: Demonstration method using in personal hygiene learning

No	Frequency Level	Quantity	Percentage
1	Always	0	0%
2	Seldom	1	16,7%
3	Never	5	83,3%
Total		6	100%

From the data gathering result about using demonstration method in personal hygiene learning, gets data that from 6 respondents, there is 1 respondent sometime use demonstration method and 5 respondents never use demonstration method. If it served in diagram, will be like this below:

Picture 2: Demonstration method using in *personal hygiene* learning

3. Picture media using in *personal hygiene* learning

Table 3: Picture media using in *personal hygiene* learning

No	Frequency Level	Quantity	Percentage
1	Always	0	0%
2	Seldom	6	100%
3	Never	0	0%
Total		6	100%

From the data gathering result about using picture media in personal hygiene learning, gets data that from 6 respondents, all respondents sometime using picture media. If it served in diagram, it will be like this below:

Picture 3: Picture media using in *personal hygiene* learning

4. Other media using in *personal hygiene* learning

Table 4: Other media using in *personal hygiene* learning

No	Frequency Level	Quantity	Percentage
1	Always	0	0%
2	Seldom	2	33,3%
3	Never	4	66,6%
Total		6	100%

From the data gathering result about other media using in personal hygiene learning, gets data that from 6 respondents, there are 2 respondents sometime use other media and 4 respondents never use other media in personal hygiene learning. If it served in diagram, will be like this below :

Picture 4: Other media using in personal hygiene learning

5. Respondent's opinion about the necessary of media in personal hygiene learning

Table 5: Respondent's opinion about the necessary of media in personal hygiene learning

No	Requirement Level	Quantity	Percentage
1	Need	6	100%
2	No need	0	0%
Total		6	100%

From the data gathering result about the necessary of media in personal hygiene learning, gets data that from 6 respondents, all respondents said that it is necessary to use media in personal hygiene learning. If it served in diagram, will be like this below :

Picture 5: Respondent's opinion about the necessary of media in personal hygiene learning

Discussion

From the research result by observation to the personal hygiene behavior children with cerebral palsy include motoric ability and cognitive obstruction indicate less hygiene. If it supports with interview result with the teacher who teach in SLB D1 YPAC Surakarta as respondents indicate that all respondents disposed to use speech method in personal hygiene learning, comparing with demonstration method using which only use by 1 respondent sometime. Picture media using sometime use by all respondents during the learning process, but in the other media using, there are only 2 respondents who use it sometime. It is most possibility cause less succeed in hygiene behavior of children with cerebral palsy, because of the limited learning media which make easier for children to understand the importance of self hygiene, reminding physically condition and limited children intelligence ability.

From all respondents opinion, say that it is necessary there's another media which can use as media to extend morally command or education values which consist in personal hygiene learning, so it can make teacher easier to share personal hygiene learning.

Conclusion And Suggestion

Based on discussion result above, we can get conclusion that it is necessary there is another learning media which can support personal hygiene learning activity, to make children easier to understanding the importance of keep clean and personal health, also

make teacher easier to share morally command about the importance of keeping self health and hygiene.

Suggestion

Need to make or create learning media which can be use to make the children easier to understand about the importance of personal hygiene and supports learning activity.

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